

VIEWS OF EASTERN THINKERS ON RAISING CHILDREN IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract. *The article provides a deep analysis of the role of the family in raising children and examines the issues of harmonizing the views of Eastern thinkers on family education with the modern pedagogical system. This study compares various views based on theoretical approaches in the works of such great scholars as Abu Nasr Farabi and Alisher Navoi, modern empirical data, and also uses historical, analytical, comparative and empirical methods.*

Key words: *family education, raising children, Eastern thinkers, pedagogical approaches, national values, empirical research, Eastern scholars, method, views.*

ВЗГЛЯДЫ ВОСТОЧНЫХ МЫСЛИТЕЛЕЙ НА ВОСПИТАНИЕ ДЕТЕЙ В СЕМЬЕ

Аннотация. *В статье дается глубокий анализ роли семьи в воспитании детей и рассматриваются вопросы гармонизации взглядов восточных мыслителей на семейное воспитание с современной педагогической системой. В данном исследовании сравниваются различные взгляды, основанные на теоретических подходах в трудах таких великих ученых, как Абу Наср Фараби и Алишер Навои, современных эмпирических данных, а также используются исторические, аналитические, сравнительные и эмпирические методы.*

Ключевые слова: *семейное воспитание, воспитание детей, восточные мыслители, педагогические подходы, национальные ценности, эмпирические исследования, восточные ученые, метод, взгляды.*

Today, with the development of human society and the strengthening of intercultural ties, the role of the family in raising children is becoming one of the most pressing issues. The views of Eastern thinkers on education and family values are of particular importance in the spiritual and moral development of mankind. These views also influence the modern education system. According to statistics, more than 70 percent of children in the world receive basic information during their upbringing in the family, which directly affects their future success in life in society. According to a UNICEF study conducted in 2023, every third child in the world faces problems of moral and intellectual development due to insufficient attention from the family. Eastern thinkers, including such great scholars as Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Alisher Navoi and Jalaluddin Rumi, emphasized the problem of family education as an important condition for achieving moral and spiritual maturity. In the modern context of globalization, changing family values and the

weakening of the education system in some regions have become pressing issues, and reorientation to the views of Eastern thinkers and national spiritual values is becoming increasingly important.

In particular, according to UNESCO, although the number of international forums on strengthening the family education system has doubled over the past five years, there have been no significant changes in practical solutions. The role of the family in raising children has been discussed in many international studies, which emphasize that the family is the main factor in the development of the child's personality. W. Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory shows that all aspects of a child's development are formed under the interrelated influence of family, school and society [1; 35]. Bronfenbrenner's research proves that social adaptation and emotional development of children are slowed down, especially in families with a high level of economic poverty. The theory of stages of psychosocial development, developed by E. Erikson, highlights the family as the main source of psychological stability and emotional development in a child's life [2; 112]. Among Eastern thinkers, in particular Uzbek scientists, in many of their works examined the role of the family in raising children. In the book of Abu Nasr al-Farabi "The City of Virtuous People" it is noted that the family is the main unit in the formation of a moral society [3; 65]. In his work "Mahbub ul-Qulub" Alisher Navoi paid special attention to moral values in the family and the upbringing of children. In his opinion, the development of society depends on upbringing and values in the family [4; 55]. Among modern Uzbek scientists, wide attention was paid to the problems of family education by A. Kadyrov, D. Karimov, H. Dzhuraev. A. Kadyrov, having studied the role of the family in the domestic education system, recommends improving this process using modern pedagogical technologies [5; 78]. Also of great importance in the study of the spiritual and moral aspects of the upbringing process in the family are the works of O. Rashidov and B. Shamsieva. O. Rashidov analyzed how parental relationships in the family affect the personal development of the child [6; 90]. The study shows that the ideas of Eastern thinkers, in particular, the spiritual and moral foundations of family education, reflected in the works of Abu Nasr al-Farabi and Alisher Navoi, still play an important role in family education today. On the other hand, the theoretical approaches of Western and CIS scientists also indicate that the family plays a key role in the psychosocial and cognitive development of the child.

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